

Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication

For Science
Communication
Professionals

Trust

Framing and Sensemaking

Power

Values and Emotion

Reflective practice

Underlying Conflicts

Ethical issues

Collaboration

Pre-Crisis

Imminent Crisis

Actual Crisis

Post-Crisis

Introduction

The **Crisis Navigator** is designed as a **strategic resource for diverse science communication stakeholders who communicate science in times of crises**. Rather than offering standardized guidelines (“what to do”), the Crisis Navigator functions as a ***sensitising tool*** – a conceptual and practical aid that helps communicators notice, reflect on, and interpret subtle aspects of their work. Here, the guiding question is: **How can science communication professionals navigate their science communication when a crisis emerges?**

This Crisis Navigator is targeted towards ***science communication professionals***, who aim to communicate complex scientific information to policymakers, communicating researchers, journalists and the public. They are also involved in inter-stakeholder collaborations to improve effective science communication during urgent societal needs.

The Crisis Navigator is structured along four stages: pre-, imminent, actual, and post-crisis, taking into account the **evolving dynamics of a crisis**. Ultimately, this Crisis Navigator serves as **a guide for science communication professionals to better imagine and anticipate what they are – and could be – up against when communicating science in times of crisis**, supporting them to navigate their practice in a more informed and reflective manner.

Challenge: Complexity and uncertainty

GUIDING QUESTION

What are good ways to convey the current state of knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics?

To answer the guiding question, consider:

Models of science communication: When conveying scientific knowledge and uncertainty to broader publics, different models of science communication offer distinct strengths and limitations. One-way communication allows science communication professionals to deliver clear information rapidly, while two-way or multi-way communication can foster trust-building and/or co-creation of knowledge. Balancing these models throughout a crisis ensures science is communicated meaningfully and effectively.

Information gaps: Science communication professionals should identify and monitor what information is available to whom, where and when; and what gaps exist or may arise that shape public understanding. It is essential to address these information gaps while avoiding overstating conclusions or creating a false sense of certainty. Examining how other crises have been communicated can help refine strategies for conveying evolving knowledge responsibly and transparently.

Science and evidence: How complex is the science? What is the evidence? Science communication professionals should aim to integrate multiple perspectives in response to these questions to offer a balanced and comprehensive understanding of an issue, while acknowledging limitations and areas of ongoing research or debate. By contextualizing disagreements and explaining the evolving nature of scientific understanding, audiences can deal with both the reliability and the uncertainty inherent in science, fostering trust rather than confusion.

Voice: Who is able to influence the state of knowledge? Who is seen as credible or trustworthy? Which voices deserve to be acknowledged, heard, and/or given a public platform – and which ones do not? Weigh the pros and cons of giving voice to particular stakeholders and types of knowledge in society, while remaining responsive to audience concerns and providing opportunities for collective exploration of scientific topics.

Clarity and simplicity: The communication of uncertainty and complexity requires clear and concise language that is accessible to a broad audience, and that avoids jargon and technical terms whenever possible. Ideally, this language breaks down concepts into understandable and relatable explanations.

Underlying conflicts

GUIDING QUESTION

What does each stakeholder need?

Underlying conflicts can stem from differences in values or interests among individuals or groups. They can exert a significant influence on attitudes, behaviors, and interactions. Science communicators can help to shed light on underlying conflicts by adopting inclusive, transparent, and participatory approaches that do not shy away from the question “What is at stake for whom and why?”. Science communication professionals should identify where interests diverge and where common ground might be found, allowing them to tailor messages more effectively, support mutual understanding, and contribute to more durable, equitable solutions during and after a crisis.

Collaboration

GUIDING QUESTION

How can science communication professionals facilitate constructive exchanges between concerned stakeholders?

Collaboration is vital in science communication to foster constructive exchanges between stakeholders and provide accurate, coordinated knowledge. Science communication professionals can promote transdisciplinarity, given their role as mediators. Collaborative structures should be built as spaces where researchers, policymakers, journalists, NGOs, and industry can work together and exchange insights and rapidly share verified information. Additionally, these networks can also be used to exchange actionable advice regarding the communication of science. Science communication professionals can focus on training stakeholders in media performance, audience engagement and bridging the gap between theory and practice. These collaborations and structures need to be established before a crisis hits, as reactive collaborations are often too slow or fragmented to meet the demands of the crisis itself.

Trust

GUIDING QUESTION

How can science communication professionals enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis?

To enable, preserve, and build trust in times of crisis, science communication professionals must engage in transparent, consistent, and empathic communication across all crisis phases. However, during the imminent and actual crisis phases, there is often little time or opportunity to build it. This makes the pre- and post-crisis phases especially important for establishing and nurturing trust among stakeholders. Multi-way science communication approaches can help to nurture trust in the pre-crisis phase, laying the foundation for more robust science communication when a crisis unfolds.

Framing and sensemaking

GUIDING QUESTION

How do different stakeholders frame and make sense of scientific information and science communication?

While framing refers to how information is presented, sensemaking concerns how individuals make sense of the information they receive. Through framing, it is possible as a sender to emphasize certain aspects of a topic while downplaying others. Science communication professionals should remain reflective of both their own framing and that of others, recognizing their potential role as mediator between stakeholders. Framing can significantly influence how an audience perceives, understands, and reacts to scientific information; yet, this does not mean that through framing science communication professionals are able to fully control how their audiences make sense of scientific knowledge. Science communication can help different audiences to make sense of scientific information in times of crises by highlighting contradictions and inherent uncertainties in an easy-to-understand way, by connecting to different personal situations and social contexts, and by tailoring messages to cultural sensitivities.

Ethical issues

GUIDING QUESTION

How can science communication promote an ethically-sound and responsible crisis response?

Science communication can facilitate responsibility, prevent misinformation, and support collaborative responses to the challenges at hand. It allows stakeholders to assess the performance of authorities and organizations and hold them accountable for their actions. It can also promote ethical public engagement by fostering trust through transparency, enabling inclusive dialogue, highlighting ethical considerations, addressing societal challenges, building partnerships, and embracing the diversity of cultural values and beliefs. An important consideration is that crises inevitably raise moral or ethical concerns and dilemmas when individuals or organizations are faced with conflicting moral principles and must make difficult decisions that have both positive and negative consequences. For instance, there may be circumstances where full transparency is not feasible or appropriate, such as when revealing certain information could jeopardize public safety or compromise ongoing investigations.

Values and emotions

GUIDING QUESTION

What is the role of values and emotions in science communication – and how do we engage with values and emotions productively?

Values and emotions are key to exploring and communicating the complexity of crises and urgent societal problems. The emotions expressed by stakeholders can reveal the values at stake and help science communicators frame the communication of science that captures the human dimension of a crisis. However, it is crucial to maintain a balance between attention to emotions and attentiveness to data, facts and evidence. Individuals rarely evaluate scientific information on evidence alone; they also respond to the emotional cues and relational signals communicators convey, such as empathy, honesty, and openness. Integrating two-way communication approaches during this crisis phase allows for meaningful expression of stakeholders' diverse values and emotions, which supports more inclusive and responsive dialogue.

Power

GUIDING QUESTION

Who has the ability to influence, shape, and control the framing and sensemaking of stakeholders and publics?

In science communication, 'power' refers to the ability to influence, shape, or control how the scientific information is framed and how different stakeholders make sense of it. These processes involve various actors – including researchers, policymakers, media professionals, and the public – each holding varying degrees of influence and authority. Questions to consider are: What counts as valid knowledge? Who decides? Whose framing prevails? Who has access to emerging technologies, such as AI, that are reshaping science communication? Understanding and navigating these power dynamics is essential for ethical and effective communication of science that fosters informed decision-making, equity, and public trust. Science communication professionals must also distinguish between competency and authority, and recognise that giving a platform to individuals outside their domain of expertise can undermine credibility and erode trust.

Reflective practice

GUIDING QUESTION

How can science communicators continuously learn from, and adapt to, crisis situations?

Once a crisis has passed its peak, it is essential that science communication professionals continue their practice, as the aftermath and long-term impacts are often just as significant as the event itself. Regular reflection on science communication across all crisis stages is equally important. Reflective practice involves critically examining responses in specific situations, recognizing how they are shaped by existing frames of thought, emotions, assumptions and worldviews. Such reflection helps science communication professionals become aware of their own positions and assumptions, especially regarding tensions and underlying conflicts that may intensify during crises. Sustained, long-term science communication can hold both authorities and science communicators themselves accountable, which helps publics to remain informed, engaged, and better prepared for future crises. By focussing on the recovery process, science communication professionals can present a more balanced narrative: One that highlights both successes and on-going challenges.

Deliverable 2.1 Science Communication Rapid Mobilisation Roadmap

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